

Part of
TeleRehaB DSS Data Management Plan

Description
TeleRehaB DSS Data Management Plan_
Retrospective_Data

Description

The pre-clinical evaluations in TeleRehaB DSS focus on the development of tools necessary to assess the patient's current status and, critically, to evaluate their risk for imminent deterioration in well-being and the likelihood of adverse incidents, such as falls, in the near future. Retrospective data is key to achieving this, allowing for the alignment of clinical modules across sites and the extraction of critical risk and prognostic factors. These include indicators for fall risk, treatment effectiveness and side effects.

Researchers

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TeleRehabilitation of Balance
clinical and economic Decision
Support System
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Description

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The retrospective data used in the TeleRehaB DSS project comes from a combination of institutions and research projects, each contributing valuable and specific datasets essential for the project's objectives. Among the institutions, the **National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA)** provided data from **248**

participants, focusing on vestibular issues, balance disorders, cognitive impairments, and fall risks in older adults. This dataset includes clinical evaluations, symptom severity, and questionnaire responses, providing critical insights into multimorbidities and fall risks in populations with vestibular disturbances or mild cognitive impairments. The **University Medical Centre Freiburg (UKLFR)** contributed data from **207 participants**, focusing on gait and balance analyses in both healthy individuals and patients with neurological and vestibular conditions. The dataset includes gait metrics such as step length and cadence, which are important for evaluating gait impairments and rehabilitation strategies. **King Chulalongkorn Memorial Hospital (KCMH)** provided a large dataset of **8,414 older adults**, focusing on fall risk, cognitive impairments, and sarcopenia. This dataset includes falls history, cognitive assessments, and physical activity metrics, offering a comprehensive population base for validating predictive models. The **University College London (UCL)** dataset includes **397 participants** and focuses on balance and neurological impairments, with data on functional gait, anxiety and depression scales, and sensor-based activity metrics, critical for analyzing gait and balance impairments. The UK Biobank dataset, planned to include 500,000 participants, remains pending but is expected to provide invaluable large-scale genetic, clinical, and lifestyle data for epidemiological analyses.

From the perspective of research projects, **HOLOBALANCE** is a European-funded initiative that focused on using digital technologies, such as virtual and augmented reality, to enhance balance rehabilitation. Its dataset includes data from **129 participants**, featuring sensor data, clinical scales like Mini-BESTest and EQ-5D-5L, and rehabilitation adherence metrics, making it a valuable resource for analyzing the effectiveness of digital rehabilitation. **EMBalance**, another European-funded project, aimed to improve the diagnosis and treatment of balance disorders by integrating clinical expertise with advanced technologies. Its dataset includes data from **989 participants**, making it one of the most extensive resources for balance-related research. The dataset includes demographics, clinical evaluations, and treatment adherence data, crucial for exploring treatment outcomes across diverse populations. **Smartbear**, a project designed to support older adults with chronic conditions, contributes data from **116 participants**, focusing on health monitoring and rehabilitation through digital tools. The dataset includes clinical assessments, wearable sensor data, and subjective

questionnaires, offering insights into the intersection of chronic conditions and mobility impairments.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

The retrospective data consist of real-world observations from previous studies. The observational data consist of previously collected and processed information such as demographics, clinical evaluations, and questionnaire responses, while the raw data are derived from sensors such as IMUs, pressure insoles, chest heart rate monitors, depth sensors, and smartwatches, capturing real-time metrics.

1.1.5 What is its format?

The data in the TeleRehaB DSS project is stored in the JSON and CSV formats.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

13KB per participant

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

The TeleRehaB DSS project aims to develop and validate a digital decision support system for older adults at risk of falls, chronic dizziness, stroke, mild cognitive impairment, vestibular disorders, or long COVID-19. The collected data will help create personalized, data-driven interventions based on the participants' functional, cognitive, and physical status.

Data collection includes baseline assessment and patient profiling, continuous evaluation of interventions, understanding functional and cognitive impacts, real-time activity monitoring and adherence measurement, qualitative insights for

system usability and experience, and data re-use. This data will be used to build on prior research, enhance data diversity and volume, and inform predictive modeling.

The scope of data collection and re-use in TeleRehaB DSS is comprehensive, covering real-time physiological data, clinical metrics, cognitive assessments, and participant feedback. The holistic approach aims to personalize interventions by understanding each participant's unique health profile, validate the efficacy of the TeleRehaB DSS system across different conditions and settings, advance digital rehabilitation technology through predictive modeling and adaptive interventions, and enable wide-scale application by ensuring the system can be effectively used in diverse healthcare environments.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The data collected includes demographic data, clinical assessments, sensor data from wearables, and usability feedback. Re-used data from previous projects and clinical partners, such as the HOLOBALANCE Project, will be used to build on previously validated data relevant to balance, gait, and cognitive impairments. The data focused on falls risk, balance disorders, vestibular disturbances, cognitive function, sarcopenia, and gait analysis. The study aimed to improve the quality of life for older adults.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Economy

Researchers studying:

- Vestibular disorder
- Long COVID-19

- Mild Cognitive Impairment
- Stroke
- Neurologists
- Human balance and its rehabilitation
- Human-machine interactions
- Signal processing
- Medical data mining

These databases will give rich, multidimensional insights into numerous aspects of human health and rehabilitation, making them a valuable resource for a wide range of studies and applications.

Researchers researching vestibular diseases, long COVID-19, moderate cognitive impairment, and stroke can benefit from these datasets since they provide a wealth of information regarding the impact of these ailments on patients' balance and mobility. This information can aid in the formulation of more efficient treatment and rehabilitation plans as well as aid in understanding how these disorders advance and how they affect patients' quality of life.

Similarly, this information can be used by neurologists and ENTs to learn more about the neurological and physiological underpinnings of balance and movement issues. This can support the identification and management of various illnesses and support the advancement of novel therapy modalities.

These datasets can also be used by researchers working in the areas of human balance and its rehabilitation, human-machine interfaces, signal processing, and medical data mining. The data can provide information about how well different rehabilitation tactics work, how people and rehabilitation devices interact, and patterns and trends in the data that might guide future study and treatments.

2 Links Between Outputs

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

A persistent and unique Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is issued to every published record on Zenodo. Moreover, DOI versioning is supported and enables users to update the record's files after they have been made public and researchers to easily cite either specific versions of a record or to cite, via a top-level DOI, all the versions of a record.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

CERIF (Common European Research Information Format)

Data are described with rich metadata

- Zenodo's metadata is compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments. As there are no specific metadata schemas that can be used with the TeleRehaB DSS data this more generic schema will be adopted.

Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes

- The DOI is a top-level and a mandatory field in the metadata of each record.

(Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

- Metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing.
- Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Registry/Catalogue

The TeleRehaB DSS project will utilize a combination of tools and systems to manage and provide access to its metadata and datasets, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles. The project will use a **Registry/Catalogue** through **Zenodo**, which assigns **Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)** to datasets, enabling their discoverability and accessibility through academic indexing services and search engines.

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

Clinical data

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

OAI-PMH protocol

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14265573>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

No

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

TeleRehaB Retrospective Dataset

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

The datasets and outputs from the TeleRehaB DSS project **are shared under clearly defined access** modes to ensure compliance with legal, ethical, and contractual obligations while promoting open science where possible. Fully anonymized datasets and metadata are shared openly via Zenodo, an open-access repository, ensuring broad accessibility. These datasets are assigned Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for discoverability and reusability and are made available under Creative Commons licenses.

For datasets containing sensitive personal information or proprietary data, restricted access conditions are applied. These datasets are only accessible to authorized researchers or institutions through a formal request process and under strict data-sharing agreements. This ensures compliance with GDPR and other relevant regulations governing the use and transfer of sensitive data. Access is granted via secure, encrypted channels to maintain data confidentiality and integrity.

Certain datasets remain closed due to legal, ethical, or contractual constraints. Datasets that cannot be fully anonymized are withheld to comply with GDPR and protect participant privacy. Additionally, data may be closed due to ethical concerns, such as the risk of participant re-identification, or to protect the legitimate interests of project beneficiaries, including intellectual property or competitive advantages. Open datasets are published in Zenodo, which ensures long-term preservation and accessibility.

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The TeleRehaB DSS project has restricted access to certain datasets or outputs due to legal, ethical, and contractual reasons. GDPR mandates restricted access to sensitive personal information, ensuring participant privacy and confidentiality. Ethical considerations are crucial, especially when data involves vulnerable populations or older adults with cognitive impairments. Contractual obligations arise from data-sharing agreements with clinical partners or third-party providers, which may impose conditions on the use or redistribution of

proprietary or licensed data. Project beneficiaries may restrict access to protect their intellectual property or proprietary methodologies. High-sensitivity datasets, such as raw sensor data or detailed clinical information, may also be restricted to prevent misuse or misinterpretation. To address these constraints, the project uses a structured approach to data sharing, with fully anonymized datasets openly shared via the Zenodo repository under Creative Commons licenses. For datasets requiring restricted access, only authorized parties can access the data under strict data-sharing agreements. This balances advancing open science with safeguarding participant privacy and the legitimate interests of all stakeholders involved.

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The TeleRehaB DSS project involves restricted access to retrospective data for authorized members of the consortium, managed by the Data Management Board (DMB) to ensure compliance with GDPR, ethical standards, and data-sharing agreements. Data will be anonymized, removing personal identifiers, and granted for specific tasks such as analysis, modeling, and integration with newly collected data. Data logs and monitoring will be in place to prevent unauthorized use.

Data will be edited, processed, and utilized during the project to support the development and validation of prediction models. This includes cleaning and standardizing data, anonymization, harmonization, feature extraction, training prediction models, validation, integration with real-time data, and simulation and testing.

After the project, retrospective datasets will be retained for the legally required period and securely stored in encrypted environments. Consortium members will continue to have restricted access to retrospective data for activities such as follow-up analyses or publications, as approved by the DMB.

External researchers may request access by submitting a formal application to the DMB, ensuring the purpose of the research, clear description of the data required, and compliance with ethical and legal standards.

Approved access will be granted under data-sharing agreements and strict licensing conditions, and datasets will be shared through secure, encrypted transfer protocols. Portions of anonymized retrospective data that comply with ethical and legal standards may be deposited in trusted repositories for broader reuse, following FAIR principles.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The dataset/output from the TeleRehaB DSS project will be made accessible for 2 years after the project has ended.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

Metadata, while structured and detailed, uses general terms and keywords instead of standardized controlled vocabularies, allowing flexibility but potentially limiting interoperability and consistency compared to controlled vocabularies.

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

The TeleRehaB DSS project aims to ensure data interoperability by adhering to established methodologies that prioritize standardization, compatibility, and FAIR principles. Key steps include using standardized formats like CSV, JSON, XLSX for different data types, making them machine-readable and compatible with various platforms and analysis tools.

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

The TeleRehaB DSS project adopts several community-endorsed best practices to ensure data and outputs are interoperable, adhering to standards that facilitate sharing, integration, and reuse across various research disciplines and platforms.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

The TeleRehaB DSS project intends to ensure the reuse of its datasets by third parties after the project concludes. A curated subset of the anonymized dataset will be made available to the broader research community under open science principles, balancing the promotion of scientific collaboration with the protection of participant confidentiality and the consortium's intellectual contributions.

To respect the intellectual contributions of the consortium, an embargo period will be implemented during which external researchers will not be permitted to publish findings using the shared data. This allows consortium members adequate time to publish their primary findings. Once the embargo period ends, external researchers can access the data subset by complying with the licensing terms and submitting applications reviewed by the Data Management Board (DMB).

The DMB will oversee data sharing and monitor usage to ensure compliance with licensing terms. Violations will result in penalties, including revocation of access and reporting to relevant ethical bodies. This framework ensures the TeleRehaB DSS dataset contributes to advancing scientific knowledge while maintaining high standards for data security, ethical compliance, and participant confidentiality.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

minor

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Direct cost

Equipment purchase costs and staff costs for preparing the data to be deposited will be covered by the project. Thus, costs are minor since they include only server maintenance costs or zero in case data are uploaded in Zenodo.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

- a. Dimitrios Fotiadis (0000-0002-7362-5082)
- b. George Matsopoulos (0000-0002-2600-9914)
- c. Doris-Eva Bamiou (0000-0001-7486-4264)

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Encryption

The TeleRehaB DSS project uses encryption as a primary security measure to protect data during storage and transmission.

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

The security measures for data security include confidentiality, integrity, availability, and compliance with GDPR and Regulatory Standards. Encryption is used for storage and transmission, safeguarding sensitive information. Backups and monitored data centers ensure data is accessible and recoverable. These measures align with GDPR standards, ensuring compliance with European Union data privacy regulations, especially for personal and health-related data.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

As we deal with patients' personal data we had to get the approval of the Ethics Committee of our institution

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Anonymising data where necessary

The data will be collected from consenting patients that will be fully informed that their de-identified and anonymized data may be used for research also after the end of the project. Details about the protocol and the information sheets and consent forms are provided in the Ethics Deliverables.

Informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation should be part of the patients' recruitment and all relevant issues should be clearly explained in the information sheets.

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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